

Teaching an Undergraduate Exploratory Data Analysis Course with R

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Abstract

Data science, as defined by the National Science Foundation (NSF) in 2014, is an interdisciplinary field focused on the comprehensive process of planning for, acquiring, managing, analyzing, and drawing inferences from data. This multifaceted domain underscores the significance of Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA), a concept aptly encapsulated by data visualization pioneer John Tukey, who stated, “The greatest value of a picture is when it forces us to notice what we never expected to see.” In this paper, we explore effective pedagogical practices for teaching EDA to undergraduate students with limited or no prior statistical background. The course predominantly leveraged R, one of the premier programming languages, for tasks such as data wrangling and visualization. Furthermore, SQL (Structured Query Language) was introduced as a crucial tool, given its relevance in fetching data from databases. Additionally, the course delved into the use of Power BI, a prominent business intelligence tool, in tandem with R for data visualizations. Complementing these efforts, we incorporated open educational resources (OER) books and projects, augmenting the learning experience and fostering a well-rounded understanding of EDA among our undergraduate students.

Key Words: Exploratory data analysis, Open educational resources, Power BI, R, SQL

1. Introduction

Data science stands as an interdisciplinary field that harnesses scientific methodologies, processes, algorithms, and systems to distill knowledge and insights from diverse, often complex data sources (Dhar, 2013). The National Science Foundation (NSF) aptly characterizes it as the “science of planning for, acquisition, management, analysis of, and inference from data” (NSF, 2014). Within this expansive domain, data analytics emerges as a specialized sub-discipline, which, in contrast to data science, tends to place greater emphasis on processing and conducting statistical analysis of existing datasets while affording comparatively less attention to data preparation, storage, and security (Aasheim et al., 2015). The significance of data analytics cannot be overstated, particularly in fast-paced industries such as healthcare, energy management, and finance, where it plays a pivotal role. The rising demand for professionals equipped with data analysis skills is evident, with a substantial 82% of organizations already employing or anticipating the need for such roles (SHRM, 2016). This demand shows no signs of waning, as highlighted by the World Economic Forum’s designation of data analyst as one of the most sought-after job categories across all sectors as we transition into the 2020s (World Economic Forum, 2016). To meet this burgeoning demand, numerous online data science and analytics programs have emerged, bridging the gap between undergraduate education and the evolving employment landscape.

Recent curriculum guidelines for undergraduate data science and analytics programs, as proposed by De Veaux (2017), underscore the importance of three foundational components: Mathematics, Statistics, and Computer Science. Mathematics and Statistics serve as the bedrock for analysis, modeling, and inference, while Computer Science equips students with the tools for data access and

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management. Traditionally, these courses have necessitated prerequisites akin to the traditional calculus sequence, encompassing Differential Calculus, Integral Calculus, Multivariate Calculus, and linear algebra, requirements that diverge from the paths of many non-STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) majors. While these mathematical prerequisites are indispensable for comprehending vital statistical concepts such as the method of Least Squares in regression modeling and other statistical estimations, many mathematical skills, such as differentiation and integration, find limited relevance in data analysis roles like Business Intelligence, Marketing analysis, and Quantitative analysis. Recognizing these challenges, universities have responded by offering non-calculus-based data analytics programs, effectively dismantling barriers to data science education for non-STEM students while they are still pursuing their degrees. This pragmatic approach acknowledges the evolving needs of data-driven fields and strives to provide accessible pathways for diverse student populations.

The Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA) course detailed in this paper was specifically tailored to cater to the needs of all students at East Stroudsburg University who possess a foundation in introductory statistics without a prerequisite of Calculus knowledge. East Stroudsburg University, situated in East Stroudsburg, Pennsylvania, is a public institution with an enrollment of approximately 5,000 students. As one of the ten constituent state universities within the Pennsylvania State System of Higher Education (PASSHE), it primarily emphasizes undergraduate education while also offering graduate programs, primarily in the field of education. The university encompasses four colleges: the College of Arts and Sciences, College of Business and Management, College of Education, and College of Health Sciences. While East Stroudsburg University does not currently offer a dedicated data science major, it does provide a statistics minor program through the Department of Mathematics, and a data science certificate program, managed by the Department of Computer Science. These programs offer courses in probability, statistics, and data analysis using R and Python. However, traditionally, these courses have demanded prerequisites in Calculus and/or Python programming, rendering them inaccessible to non-STEM students aspiring to delve into data science. In response to this gap, the EDA course was introduced in Fall 2022, exclusively designed for students with a grounding in introductory statistics but lacking Calculus prerequisites. R was chosen as the primary programming language for the course due to its prominent position as one of the essential open-source data science tools, alongside Python and Julia. The decision was substantiated by R's specialized design for data analysis and the interactive data science environment offered by RStudio, as outlined in Wickham and Grolemund's (2023) work.

In this paper, I present the topics covered in the EDA course in Section 2 and course evaluations in Section 3. A discussion about the design of future teaching of the course follows in the Discussion section.

2. Topics Covered in the EDA Course

The lecture slides, R cheat sheets and data sets used in the lecture slides for the EDA course are available on the author's GitHub website https://github.com/esumath/MATH_318. I summarize the main topics covered in the lecture slides in this section.

2.1 Data Manipulation and Data Visualization with R

R is a specialized programming language tailored for statistical computing and graphical analysis, endorsed by both the R Core Team and the R Foundation for Statistical Computing (R Core Team, 2023). In the realm of data science, R, Python, and SAS reign supreme as the top three programming languages for statistical data analysis. While both R and Python are open source, Python serves as a versatile general-purpose programming language, whereas R is meticulously designed for data analysis. R is an offspring of the S programming language, deeply rooted in the discipline of data analysis, as opposed to traditional programming language origins. It shares the same fundamental philosophy as S, prioritizing user-friendly, interactive environments where programming isn't the forefront consideration. Instead, users can smoothly transition into programming as their needs

evolve and sophistication grows, with language and system intricacies taking on greater significance, in alignment with the insights of S language developer John Chambers, as articulated by Peng (2016): “We wanted users to be able to begin in an interactive environment, where they did not consciously think of themselves as programming. Then as their needs became clearer and their sophistication increased, they should be able to slide gradually into programming, when the language and system aspects would become more important.” In terms of ease of acquisition, R offers a gentler learning curve in comparison to Python. The open-source nature of R has contributed significantly to its burgeoning popularity, facilitated by its ability to execute a broad spectrum of statistical and graphical techniques. Notably, the active and dynamic developer community has ushered in an impressive array of over 18,000 R add-on packages – code created to enrich the core language and tackle specific problem types (Wickham, 2015). These packages augment R’s capabilities, making it an exceptionally versatile tool for data analysis and visualization.

R was selected as the platform for our Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA) course, primarily due to its widespread adoption within the data science community. As Joshua Blumenstock (2013, <https://www.jblumenstock.com/teaching/course=infx573>) aptly described, “A data scientist is someone who knows more statistics than a computer scientist and more computer science than a statistician”. In contrast, a data analyst is focused on sourcing, organizing, and dissecting information from diverse origins to drive an organization's strategic objectives. While data scientists typically employ high-level general-purpose languages like Java and Python, data analysts lean on a variety of tools to gather data, perform statistical analyses, and derive actionable insights to inform critical business decisions. For data analysts, the need for developing applications or data pipelines using a general-purpose language is generally less pronounced. R, purpose-built for data analysis, boasts a user-friendly, spreadsheet-like data structure called a “data frame” that streamlines the application of calculations. Notably, R has steadily ascended to the position of the preferred programming language for data analysis. Its accessibility is a significant draw, allowing individuals with limited programming experience to learn R efficiently. Consequently, R serves as the ideal choice for conducting data manipulation and data visualization within our EDA course.

The EDA course encompasses four primary domains of study: data refinement, employing a combination of R’s core functions and supplementary add-on packages like dplyr (Wickham et al., 2023) and tidyr (Wickham, Vaughan, and Girlich, 2023); data visualization, where a spectrum of statistical charts, including histograms and scatter plots, come to the forefront; the creation of interactive dashboards facilitated by the R package flexdashboard (Aden-Buie et al., 2023); and the development of web applications utilizing the R package shiny (Chang et al., 2023). The initial segment of the course (Lecture 01 - 06) is dedicated to establishing a firm grasp of the fundamental programming syntaxes of R, encompassing topics like R data types, data structures, operators, conditional statements, loops, functions, data input and output procedures, and the production of statistical graphs using R’s core functions. Subsequently, the focus pivots toward the application of R add-on packages for the aforementioned areas of study. The appeal of these packages lies in their ability to streamline data analysis tasks, offering a more concise and efficient coding approach when compared to relying solely on R’s base functions.

Data cleaning or data wrangling is the process of detecting and correcting (or removing) corrupt or inaccurate records from a record set, table, or database and refers to identifying incomplete, incorrect, inaccurate or irrelevant parts of the data and then replacing, modifying, or deleting the dirty or coarse data (Wu, 2013). It is imperative to recognize that data analysis can only be executed effectively with high-quality, pristine data. In our course, we delve into this pivotal subject matter in Lectures 10 through 13. To equip students with the necessary tools and techniques for efficient data cleaning, we introduce three key R packages: dplyr (Wickham et al., 2023), tidyr (Wickham, Vaughan, and Girlich, 2023), and tibble (Müller Wickham, 2023). These packages are integral components of the tidyverse ecosystem, a thoughtfully curated assembly of R packages purpose-built for the field of data science. All tidyverse packages share a unified design philosophy, grammar, and data structures, ensuring seamless compatibility and cooperation. Furthermore, the tidyverse includes the readr package (Wickham and Hester, 2023), tailored for the rapid and user-

friendly ingestion of extensive rectangular data. Throughout the course, students acquire the proficiency to employ these R packages, empowering them to efficiently clean unruly datasets and lay the groundwork for robust data analysis.

The focal point of exploratory data analysis (EDA) lies in the art of data visualization. Understanding data generally involves an iterative cycle of visualization and modeling (Meloncon and Warner, 2017). A well-crafted visualization possesses the unique power to reveal more about data than any other tool in the data analyst's arsenal, a sentiment echoed by John Tukey, who stated that the greatest value of a picture is when it forces us to notice what we never expected to see (Tukey, 1977). Data visualizations have the ability to unveil unforeseen patterns, spark new inquiries, and, at times, even hint that the questions being posed might need re-evaluation. R equips users with inherent capabilities for constructing statistical charts and graphs, though achieving the desired aesthetics, including labels, line types, spacing, font sizes, and transparency, necessitates meticulous parameter adjustments. This is where the R package `ggplot2` (Wickham et al., 2023) steps in, offering aesthetic mappings that define the relationship between data variables and their visual attributes. A striking advantage of `ggplot2`, in contrast to base R functions, is its flexibility in setting aesthetic mappings both within the main `ggplot()` function and in individual layers. This streamlined approach empowers users to generate captivating graphs with significantly less code and a more intuitive syntax, eliminating the need to grapple with complex programming logic and graphic devices in R. A compelling illustration is found in the ease with which `ggplot2` handles graph faceting based on categorical variables. While base R demands data division into separate sub-datasets to plot individual segments, each corresponding to a level of the categorical variable, `ggplot2` simplifies the process by introducing a layer of faceting code without necessitating data splitting. This ease of use renders `ggplot2` particularly welcoming to newcomers. Lectures 07 and 08 introduce `ggplot2` to the class, equipping students with a potent tool for their EDA journey.

Interactive graphs offer audiences a richer, more engaging experience compared to their static counterparts when accessible through web browsers or websites. Within our EDA course, we integrate three essential R packages, namely, `plotly` (Sievert et al., 2023), `flexdashboard` (Aden-Buie et al., 2023), and `shiny` (Chang et al., 2023), to unlock the potential of interactivity in data presentation. The R `plotly` package empowers users to craft interactive web graphics effortlessly, all without the need for JavaScript code. This is achieved by initializing a `plotly` object or transforming a `ggplot2` object into a `plotly` format, granting users the ability to create captivating, interactive graphs. Moreover, both `ggplot2` and `plotly` draw inspiration from the grammar of graphics (Wilkinson et al., 2005), resulting in highly similar syntax, thereby facilitating the learning curve for students and simplifying data visualization techniques. The R `flexdashboard` package is a formidable tool for simplifying the development of interactive, visually appealing dashboards and reports. It empowers users to craft dynamic and responsive dashboards, seamlessly shareable as standalone HTML documents or integrated into larger web applications, all without the need for deep expertise in web development technologies like JavaScript, HTML, or CSS. In parallel, the R `Shiny` package emerges as a powerful resource for constructing interactive, data-driven web applications directly from R. A significant advantage of `Shiny` is its accessibility, as it requires no prior web development skills. Leveraging existing R code, libraries, and data manipulation skills, users can seamlessly construct web applications, making it a valuable asset for R practitioners, even those without substantial web development experience. Instructors, too, have harnessed `Shiny` to enhance statistics students' learning experiences (Doi, Potter, Wong, et al., 2016). Furthermore, a wealth of `Shiny` web apps (<https://shiny.rstudio.com/gallery/>) has been created for data analysis and visualization, exemplified by resources like `Rstats` (Yang, Antony, Bahl, and Health, 2020), employed for linear model fitting, survival analysis, and ANOVA tests. These valuable topics are expounded upon in Lectures 21, 23, and 24. The course also delves into the dynamic realm of animated graphs, introducing students to the `magick` package (Ooms, 2023) and `ganimate` (Pedersen and Robinson, 2022) in Lecture 20, enabling the creation of compelling animations. Additionally, Lecture 22 explores the creation of choropleth maps using various R packages, enriching students' skillset for geographical data visualization.

2.2 SQL and Data Visualization with Power BI

The topics of SQL (Structured Query Language) and Power BI are covered in Lecture 25 – 32.

In today's data-driven landscape, businesses and organizations grapple with copious volumes of data stored within databases. Managing this data efficiently requires the use of specialized software known as a Database Management System (DBMS). A DBMS is tasked with the efficient storage and retrieval of vast data sets, enabling data to persist over extended periods. The world of databases encompasses various types of systems, with relational databases and NoSQL (Not Only SQL) databases being prominent examples. At the heart of managing relational databases lies SQL, or Structured Query Language, a versatile and pervasive tool. SQL empowers users to execute a broad spectrum of operations, including data querying, record updates, data insertion, and even the definition of database structures. Prior to delving into this topic, our students have already gained experience in working with multiple data sets using R's data wrangling packages. For instance, they are familiar with using base R's `merge()` function and functions within the `dplyr` package (Wickham et al., 2023) for tasks like inner joins, left joins, right joins, or full joins across two or more data sets. However, they may not have encountered the concept of databases. To bridge this gap, I introduced the fundamental concepts of relational databases and SQL in Lecture 26, followed by a thorough exploration of basic SQL syntax in Lectures 27 to 30. In the expansive landscape of open-source database software packages, notable options include MySQL and SQLite. For our class, we have chosen the open-source PostgreSQL due to its user-friendly installation process and robust performance. It's important to note that the database industry is vast and continually growing, resulting in a high demand for individuals skilled in database management. Proficiency in SQL is an invaluable asset for our students, one that will significantly benefit their future careers.

In the realm of Business Intelligence (BI), data visualization has gained immense popularity, offering the capability to transform data into actionable insights without the need for coding. BI, which revolves around the practice of deriving insights from data to guide business decisions, is a pivotal aspect of modern enterprises. In our course, Lectures 25, 31, and 32 delve into the subject of BI, specifically focusing on Microsoft Power BI. This powerful and versatile tool has played a pivotal role in revolutionizing the field of business intelligence. Microsoft's journey into self-service Business Intelligence (BI) began in 2009 with the introduction of Power Pivot for Microsoft Excel 2010. It was later developed into a standalone software solution. One of Power BI's notable strengths lies in its ability to enable data visualization, reporting, and dashboard creation without the need for coding skills. Within Power BI, Data Analysis Expressions (DAX) functions come into play, allowing users to construct formulas and expressions, akin to Excel formulas. Moreover, Power BI empowers users to seamlessly query databases using SQL (Structured Query Language) directly within the tool, streamlining data integration. Another compelling reason for the inclusion of Power BI in our course curriculum is its capacity to extend data visualization functionalities significantly. This is achieved by integrating the capabilities of programming languages such as R and Python. In scenarios where the built-in Power BI visualization tools fall short, users can seamlessly incorporate R to create custom graphs and perform data wrangling tasks, thanks to its seamless integration with the platform.

2.3 Utilizing Open-Source Resources

Throughout the course, a diverse range of open educational resources were thoughtfully integrated to enhance students' learning experience. These resources include R package documentation and assistance directly accessible within RStudio, empowering students to navigate coding challenges efficiently. Additionally, the course drew inspiration from the book *R for Data Science* by Wickham and Golemund, an influential text from O'Reilly Media, which provided valuable insights and practical knowledge. For mastering Git and GitHub, "Happy Git and GitHub for the user" served as an indispensable guide. To bolster SQL skills, the tutorials on `w3schools` proved invaluable. For interactive data visualizations, Plotly R emerged as a powerful tool. The course also ventured into web app development through Shiny, leveraging resources from

<https://shiny.posit.co/r/getstarted/shiny-basics/lesson1/index.html>. Furthermore, a hands-on Power BI workshop titled “Dashboard in a Day” by Microsoft was introduced to students for self-learning. Lecture slides for the course were made readily available on GitHub, ensuring accessibility and easy reference for other students or instructors (https://github.com/esumath/MATH_318). These open resources collectively enriched the educational landscape, fostering a comprehensive and engaging learning environment. The following is a list of references with clickable link.

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- Plotly R <https://plotly.com/r/> for interactive data visualizations
- Shiny <https://shiny.posit.co/r/getstarted/shiny-basics/lesson1/index.html> for web app development.
- Dashboard in a Day <https://powerbi.microsoft.com/en-us/diad/> which is hands-on Power BI workshop
- The lecture slides of this EDA course is available on GitHub https://github.com/esumath/MATH_318

3. Course Evaluations

The course evaluations consist of homework assignments or small data analysis projects, in-class quizzes, and a culminating final project. Each week of the course is carefully structured to feature three 50-minute lectures during which students actively engage with the lecture slides to gain a deep understanding of coding intricacies. Encouragingly, the use of Rmarkdown is highly recommended, enabling students to include comments when they take class notes and knit the class notes as a html or pdf format report. Furthermore, every week introduces R homework assignments, which are essentially data analysis challenges that prompt students to apply their newly acquired coding skills to real-world scenarios. To gauge their comprehension and practical application of the material, in-class open-book quizzes are regularly conducted, affording students opportunities to showcase their mastery. As for the final project, students are provided with a selection of data sets sourced from Tidytuesday (<https://github.com/rfordatascience/tidytuesday>). These data sets require thorough cleaning before they can be subjected to data analysis. While students have the option to collaborate in groups for working on a same data set, it is imperative that they independently compose their project reports to demonstrate their individual understanding and proficiency.

Discussion

Looking ahead to future updates for this EDA course, several exciting enhancements are under consideration. Firstly, there is a plan to incorporate data visualization of statistical inferences, enriching students’ understanding of the analytical process. Additionally, the inclusion of the Python programming language in the curriculum is on the horizon, although it will necessitate a prerequisite understanding of Python programming for students. To further elevate the teaching and class management experience, exploration of new R packages such as learnr (Aden-Buie et al., 2023) for interactive tutorial creation using R Markdown and ghclass (Rundel and Cetinkaya-Rundel, 2022) for GitHub-based course management is on the agenda. Lastly, an exciting prospect is the integration of AI tools like ChatGPT and GitHub Copilot into the class, adding a layer of artificial intelligence-driven assistance and innovation to the learning journey. These proposed updates aim to continually enhance the quality and relevance of the EDA course, keeping it at the forefront of data science education.

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